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Management modeling of financial evaluation of economic and innovative activities of industrial enterprises in conditions of digitalization, management of professional development projects and formation of marketing strategy

Relevance of the research topic. Management modeling of financial evaluation of economic and innovative activities of industrial enterprises in conditions of digitalization, management of professional development projects and formation of marketing strategy is an important topic of research. Industrial enterprises currently have low adaptive capabilities, in this context, such modeling will significantly improve their activities.

Formulation of the problem. The problems of modeling the management of financial evaluation of economic and innovative activities of industrial enterprises in the conditions of digitalization, management of professional development projects and the formation of a marketing strategy are very important and relevant topics for research in today's conditions. However, at this time, there is almost no methodology for evaluating the activity of industrial enterprises, which is an extremely important task, taking into account the unstable external environment.

Setting the goal and objectives of the research – to propose a procedure for modeling the management of financial evaluation of economic and innovative activities of industrial enterprises in the conditions of digitalization, management of professional development projects and the formation of a marketing strategy.

Research method or methodology. In order to implement the modeling procedure, we used the taxonomic method, as well as the method of statistical generalization.

Field of application of results. The proposed modeling technique will be useful for managers of industrial enterprises who are concerned with the problem of their effective functioning.

Conclusions according to the article. A methodology for modeling the management of financial

evaluation of economic and innovative activities of industrial enterprises in the conditions of digitalization, management of professional development projects and formation of a marketing strategy is proposed. The specified technique will be useful for the effective operation of industrial enterprises in conditions of uncertainty and changes in the external environment.

Keywords: *management, financial evaluation, innovative activity, digitalization, management of professional development projects, marketing strategy, industrial enterprises.*

НАГОЛЮК О. Є., СКРИПНИК В. В.,
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Моделювання менеджменту фінансового оцінювання господарської та інноваційної діяльності промислових підприємств в умовах діджиталізації, управління проектами підвищення кваліфікації та формування маркетингової стратегії

Актуальність теми дослідження. Моделювання менеджменту фінансового оцінювання господарської та інноваційної діяльності промислових підприємств в умовах діджиталізації, управління проектами підвищення кваліфікації та формування маркетингової стратегії є важливою тематикою дослідження. Промислові підприємства на цей час мають низькі адаптаційні можливості, у такому контексті таке моделювання значно покращить їх діяльність.

Постановка проблеми. Проблематика моделювання менеджменту фінансового оцінювання господарської та інноваційної діяльності промислових підприємств в умовах діджиталізації, управління проектами підвищення кваліфікації та формування маркетингової стратегії є дуже важливою та актуальною тематикою в умовах сьогодення. Однак на цей час майже відсутня методика оцінювання діяльності промислових підприємств, що є вкрай важливою задачею з урахуванням нестабільного зовнішнього середовища.

Постановка мети і завдань дослідження – запропонувати процедуру моделювання менеджменту фінансового оцінювання господарської та інноваційної діяльності промислових підприємств в умовах діджиталізації, управління проектами підвищення кваліфікації та формування маркетингової стратегії.

Метод або методологія дослідження. З метою реалізації процедури моделювання нами використано таксономічний метод, а також метод статистичного узагальнення.

Галузь застосування результатів. Запропонована методика моделювання буде корисною для менеджерів промислових підприємств, які опікуються проблемою їх ефективного функціонування.

Висновки за статтею. Запропоновано методику моделювання менеджменту фінансового оцінювання господарської та інноваційної діяльності промислових підприємств в умовах діджиталізації, управління проектами підвищення кваліфікації та формування маркетингової стратегії. Зазначена методика буде корисною для ефективної діяльності промислових підприємств в умовах невизначеності та зміни зовнішнього середовища.

Ключові слова: менеджмент, фінансове оцінювання, інноваційна діяльність, діджиталізація, управління проектами підвищення кваліфікації, маркетингова стратегія, промислові підприємства.

Formulation of the problem. The problems of modeling the management of financial evaluation of economic and innovative activities of industrial enterprises in the conditions of digitalization, management of professional development projects and the formation of a marketing strategy are very important and relevant topics for research in today's conditions. However, at this time, there is almost no methodology for evaluating the activity of industrial enterprises,

which is an extremely important task, taking into account the unstable external environment.

Analysis of recent research and publications. In scientific works, there is almost no methodology for modeling the management of financial evaluation of economic and innovative activities of industrial enterprises in the conditions of digitalization, management of professional development projects and formation of a marketing strategy. Some questions

were considered by such scientists as: Zos–Kior M., Shcherbak V., Gryshchenko I., Ganushchak–Efimenko L., Hnatenko I., Nifatova O. However, the modern world does not stand still, but is constantly moving [1–17]. The conditions and rules of operation of industrial enterprises are changing. Therefore, such research is extremely important.

Formulation of the goals of the article (statement of the task) – to propose a procedure for modeling the management of financial evaluation of economic and innovative activities of industrial enterprises in the conditions of digitalization, management of professional development projects and formation of a marketing strategy.

Presenting main material. Modeling management of financial evaluation of economic and innovative activities of industrial enterprises in the conditions of digitalization, management of professional development projects and formation of marketing strategy are proposed to be carried out using taxonomic analysis. The taxonomy method is an important tool for analyzing the level of economic development of the system. This method allows you to structure and generalize multidimensional statistical material that characterizes the system in time and space. Using the taxonomy method, a large number of different indicators can be summarized into a few key characteristics or categories. This allows a better understanding of the economic state of the system, and also makes it easier to compare it with other systems or with past states of the system itself. Such analysis can serve as a basis for decision–making in the field of management, allowing a better understanding of current problems and opportunities.

Taxonomic modeling can be useful for analyzing the reserve and financial capacity of the enterprise. The use of taxonomic methods allows the segregation of data presented in the form of expressions into different groups, which helps to understand the internal structure of the studied objects and the problems of their functioning. These methods allow obtaining important information that can be obtained in neural modeling using artificial networks. So, taxonomic modeling allows you to generalize, segment and classify large data sets that reflect the properties of internal resources or potentials of a business entity. It helps to understand the structure and features of these resources for further management and strategic decision–making.

Thus, the algorithm for modeling the management of financial evaluation of economic and innovative activities of industrial enterprises in the conditions of digitalization, management of professional development projects and the formation of a marketing strategy using taxonomic modeling will have certain actions: standardization of indicators, dispersion equalization, hierarchization of features, integration of the general indicator. In this case, we will conduct a taxonomic analysis of innovative, financial, and industrial marketing indicators of the activity of the branches of Ukraine for the last eleven years according to the algorithm for calculating the taxonomic indicator (taxonomy coefficient), in particular: the number of innovatively active industrial enterprises, the costs of innovation of industrial enterprises, the number of names of introduced innovative types of products by industrial enterprises, the number of industrial enterprises that introduced innovations, the number of industrial enterprises that sold innovative products and the volume of sold innovative products. The research, calculation, analysis and forecasting of economic indicators of the activity of industries was carried out in the cross–section of industries for the last eleven years according to the data of the State Statistics Service of Ukraine for 2012–2022. At the first stage of the taxonomic analysis of the indicators of the activity of industries of Ukraine, we formulate a data matrix for the study of the system, using data from the past eleven years. The list of indicators of the activity of the industrial branches of Ukraine by the directions of analytical research, which form the matrix of observations for the last eleven years, is presented in the block of the table. 1.

Further, at this preparatory stage, the average value and standard deviation of the signs of the activity of the branches of industry of Ukraine, 2012–2022, were determined by the corresponding built–in statistical functions of Microsoft Excel electronic spreadsheets (table block 2).

At the next stage, it is possible to conditionally divide the activity indicators of Ukrainian industries, which directly or indirectly affect the current state of this economy as follows: (Table 3). However, it should be noted that such a division is conditional and is based exclusively for calculations by the method of taxonomic analysis of the activity of Ukrainian industries.

Table 1. Dynamics of activity indicators of Ukrainian industries for taxonomic analysis, generalized fragment for 2022

Industries	2022					
	Number of innovatively active industrial enterprises (units)	Costs for innovation of industrial enterprises (thousand UAH)	Number of industrial enterprises that introduced innovations (units)	The number of names of innovative types of products introduced by industrial enterprises (units)	The number of industrial enterprises that implemented innovative products (units)	The amount realized innovative products (thousand UAH)
Mining industry	25	1640700,00	17	44	11	5817833,00
Processing industry, including	730	3302592,00	668	4006	556	41538460,00
production of food products, beverages and tobacco products	191		176	1079	142	6664121,00
textile production, production of clothes, leather, leather products and other materials	19		17	27	15	110273,00
wood processing and production of wood products, except furniture	19		17	91	14	473071,00
pulp and paper production;	19	147502,00	13		11	149685,00
publishing activity	5		2		2	
production of coke, oil refining products	52	861127,00	48	299	40	650818,00
chemical and petrochemical industry	34	1846390,00	33	253	31	1438518,00
production of basic	82	532516,00	72	175	53	1576515,00
pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations	65	2088693,00	61	300	48	739511,00
production of rubber and plastic products, other non-metallic mineral products	36	333731,00	34	100	34	1293497,00
metallurgical production, production of finished metal products, except for the production of machines and equipment	26	1294981,00	67	570	58	3571537,00
production of computers, electronic and optical products	40	515674,00	38	220	34	2442555,00
production of machines and equipment	48	465619,00	46	368	38	2910969,00
production of electrical and electronic and optical equipment	24	68625,00	44	176	36	514291,00
production of transport equipment	26	374539,00	15		5	
other industries	28	69864,00	18		1	

Source: <https://www.ukrstat.gov.ua/>

Table 2. Calculation of the average value and standard deviation of the indicators of the activity of the industrial sectors of Ukraine, 2012–2022

Industries	On average, 2012–2022. The average value of the feature					
	Number of innovatively active industrial enterprises (units)	Costs for innovation of industrial enterprises (thousand UAH)	Number of industrial enterprises that introduced innovations (units)	The number of names of innovative types of products introduced by industrial enterprises (units)	The number of industrial enterprises that implemented innovative products (units)	The amount realized innovative products (thousand UAH)
Mining industry	31	972905,08	21	16	10	803251,03
Processing industry, including	1070	9702441,12	904	3190	738	31235669,73
production of food products, beverages and tobacco products	268	1667587,62	229	706	192	5665297,70
textile production, production of clothes, leather, leather products and other materials	54	78748,47	42	86	28	195928,80
wood processing and production of wood products, except furniture	56	307823,11	43	101	31	570264,66
pulp and paper production;	49	200764,20	34	24	21	435052,60
publishing activity	8	93070,82	5	48	3	5598829,66
production of coke, oil refining products	86	706909,79	72	221	62	1637961,01
chemical and petrochemical industry	32	1010579,73	29	160	28	842032,34
production of basic	94	613874,56	75	165	54	1140241,35
pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations	96	3286539,85	82	278	65	5255259,51
production of rubber and plastic products, other non-metallic mineral products	44	227533,13	40	92	35	807327,67
metallurgical production, production of finished metal products, except for the production of machines and equipment	119	1189399,48	109	709	93	3915701,60
production of computers, electronic and optical products	78	351505,56	67	214	60	1751518,05
production of machines and equipment	67	934447,65	61	207	53	3409580,84
production of electrical and electronic and optical equipment	62	126508,72	54	187	41	389206,25
production of transport equipment	60	1011202,62	35	23	5	38631,58
other industries	31	64471,70	19	19	4	78899,23
Industries	Standard deviation is a built-in statistical function STDEV.P					
	Number of innovatively active industrial enterprises (units)	Costs for innovation of industrial enterprises (thousand UAH)	Number of industrial enterprises that introduced innovations (units)	The number of names of innovative types of products introduced by industrial enterprises (units)	The number of industrial enterprises that implemented innovative products (units)	The amount realized innovative products (thousand UAH)
Mining industry	12	661549,72	8	14	4	1683784,64
Processing industry, including	384	4392440,26	275	625	230	7884419,08

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production of food products, beverages and tobacco products	103	694796,66	76	180	63	898493,82
textile production, production of clothes, leather, leather products and other materials	22	20576,79	14	46	11	114806,29
wood processing and production of wood products, except furniture	40	241033,41	26	136	17	367030,43
pulp and paper production;	22	115405,10	13	7	8	303785,79
publishing activity	4	90007,11	3	61	2	5321593,79
production of coke, oil refining products	59	746287,53	50	105	41	1033850,03
chemical and petrochemical industry	2	506910,44	3	53	3	288141,30
production of basic	39	295422,75	23	67	18	489290,11
pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations	32	4120367,30	24	122	20	3281035,80
production of rubber and plastic products, other non-metallic mineral products	15	109389,19	12	25	10	288820,41
metallurgical production, production of finished metal products, except for the production of machines and equipment	56	189098,99	44	197	38	1396376,79
production of computers, electronic and optical products	49	153064,20	41	96	38	681840,44
production of machines and equipment	16	414765,40	13	88	13	1408017,50
production of electrical and electronic and optical equipment	29	55154,43	17	92	12	141047,87
production of transport equipment	39	1450986,67	18	22	2	44878,36
other industries	12	50815,23	5	24	3	104544,47

Source: calculated by the authors

Table 3. Definition of the reference vector: for stimulants - the maximum value of the standardized indicator; for the destimulator - the minimum value of the signs of the activity of the industrial branches of Ukraine, 2012–2022

Industries	Standard (stimulator - max; destimulator - min)					
	Number of innovatively active industrial enterprises (units) Destimulator	Costs for innovation of industrial enterprises (thousand UAH) Stimulator	The number of industrial enterprises that introduced innovations (units) Stimulator	The number of names of innovative types of products introduced by industrial enterprises (units) Destimulator	Number of industrial enterprises that implemented innovative products (units) Stimulator	Volume of implemented innovative products (thousand UAH) Stimulator
Mining industry	-1,64	2,47	2,30	-1,06	2,01	2,98
Processing industry, including	-1,01	2,63	1,36	-1,69	1,24	1,39
production of food products, beverages and tobacco products	-1,06	2,25	1,57	-1,40	1,42	1,79
textile production, production of clothes, leather, leather products and other materials	-1,57	1,77	1,33	-1,66	1,43	2,10
wood processing and production of wood products, except furniture	-1,10	1,88	2,07	-0,70	2,13	1,98

pulp and paper production;	-2,26	1,63	1,35	-3,16	1,22	1,64
publishing activity	-1,14	1,81	1,98	-0,80	1,68	2,04
production of coke, oil refining products	-0,88	2,74	1,76	-1,62	1,76	2,08
chemical and petrochemical industry	-13,14	1,65	1,40	-2,99	2,00	2,07
production of basic	-0,98	1,62	2,41	-1,08	2,31	1,95
pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations	-0,99	2,72	1,30	-2,04	1,31	2,48
production of rubber and plastic products, other non-metallic mineral products	-2,88	2,22	1,84	-3,66	1,63	1,68
metallurgical production, production of finished metal products, except for the production of machines and equipment	-1,66	1,19	1,66	-1,43	1,69	1,59
production of computers, electronic and optical products	-0,85	1,84	1,71	-1,36	1,65	1,48
production of machines and equipment	-1,35	2,01	1,65	-1,89	1,48	2,58
production of electrical and electronic and optical equipment	-1,34	1,61	2,65	-1,01	2,24	2,30
production of transport equipment	-1,12	2,77	1,96	-1,04	1,96	1,53
other industries	-2,62	2,06	1,45	-0,82	1,88	1,41

Source: calculated by the authors

Next, the distances between individual indicators of innovative activity and the standard vector are determined and the values are calculated, which are the input values used to calculate the coefficient of the taxonomy of the activity of the industries of Ukraine, 2012–2022.

Table 4. Determination of the average distance between individual variables and the reference vector of the components of the activity system of the industrial sectors of Ukraine, 2012–2022

Industries	1. Average distance					
	Number of innovatively active industrial enterprises (units)	Costs for innovation of industrial enterprises (thousand UAH)	Number of industrial enterprises that introduced innovations (units)	The number of names of innovative types of products introduced by industrial enterprises (units)	The number of industrial enterprises that implemented innovative products (units)	The amount realized innovative products (thousand UAH)
Mining industry	1,06	1,47	1,39	0,80	1,24	1,75
Processing industry, including	0,79	1,55	0,93	1,08	0,88	1,27
production of food products, beverages and tobacco products	0,81	1,51	1,03	0,95	0,96	1,73
textile production, production of clothes, leather, leather products and other materials	1,03	1,42	0,92	1,07	0,97	1,38
wood processing and production of wood products, except furniture	0,82	1,24	1,27	0,67	1,30	1,31
pulp and paper production;	0,92	1,55	1,75	1,11	1,66	1,45
publishing activity	0,84	1,23	1,23	0,56	1,08	1,29
production of coke, oil refining products	0,74	1,61	1,12	1,05	1,12	1,36
chemical and petrochemical industry	6,21	1,39	3,64	1,57	3,51	1,95
production of basic	0,78	1,05	1,44	0,81	1,39	1,36
pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations	0,78	1,60	0,91	1,26	0,91	1,56
production of rubber and plastic products, other non-metallic mineral products	1,44	1,69	1,77	1,79	1,69	1,72

metallurgical production, production of finished metal products, except for the production of machines and equipment	1,07	0,86	1,07	0,97	1,08	1,23
production of computers, electronic and optical products	0,73	1,16	1,09	0,93	1,07	1,16
production of machines and equipment	0,93	1,24	1,07	1,18	0,99	1,68
production of electrical and electronic and optical equipment	0,92	1,05	1,57	0,78	1,36	1,57
production of transport equipment	0,83	1,63	1,22	0,68	1,21	1,16
other industries	1,32	1,45	1,78	0,48	1,39	1,14

Source: Calculated by the authors

Table 5. Determination of the root mean square deviation of the value of the characteristics of the industrial sectors of Ukraine, 2012–2022

Industries	2. Mean square deviation					
	Number of innovatively active industrial enterprises (units)	Costs for innovation of industrial enterprises (thousand UAH)	Number of industrial enterprises that introduced innovations (units)	The number of names of innovative types of products introduced by industrial enterprises (units)	The number of industrial enterprises that implemented innovative products (units)	The amount realized innovative products (thousand UAH)
Mining industry	11,55	22,13	19,66	6,59	15,74	31,37
Processing industry, including	6,32	24,62	8,89	12,01	7,91	16,38
production of food products, beverages and tobacco products	6,65	23,25	10,85	9,22	9,41	30,53
textile production, production of clothes, leather, leather products and other materials	10,76	20,61	8,62	11,73	9,54	19,51
wood processing and production of wood products, except furniture	6,90	15,72	16,48	4,63	17,24	17,45
pulp and paper production;	8,68	24,49	31,29	12,47	28,01	21,32
publishing activity	7,16	15,48	15,32	3,25	11,94	17,01
production of coke, oil refining products	5,54	26,45	12,83	11,26	12,72	18,87
chemical and petrochemical industry	393,65	19,72	135,57	25,30	125,56	38,75
production of basic	6,13	11,32	21,19	6,78	19,78	18,75
pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations	6,19	26,13	8,37	16,09	8,44	24,97
production of rubber and plastic products, other non-metallic mineral products	21,03	29,24	31,87	32,66	29,20	30,35
metallurgical production, production of finished metal products, except for the production of machines and equipment	11,73	7,52	11,70	9,53	12,00	15,44
production of computers, electronic and optical products	5,38	13,71	12,20	8,87	11,58	13,67
production of machines and equipment	8,83	15,73	11,59	14,28	9,98	28,76
production of electrical and electronic and optical equipment	8,70	11,23	25,09	6,28	18,82	25,10
production of transport equipment	7,04	27,01	15,14	4,72	15,06	13,77
other industries	17,82	21,32	32,44	2,36	19,72	13,22

Source: Calculated by the authors

Table 6. Determination of the total distance between the performance indicators of Ukrainian industries, 2012–2022, and the benchmark

Industries	3. The total distance between the indicators and the benchmark					
	Number of innovatively active industrial enterprises (units)	Costs for innovation of industrial enterprises (thousand UAH)	Number of industrial enterprises that introduced innovations (units)	The number of names of innovative types of products introduced by industrial enterprises (units)	The number of industrial enterprises that implemented innovative products (units)	The amount realized innovative products (thousand UAH)
Mining industry	24,17	45,73	40,70	13,98	32,71	64,48
Processing industry, including	13,43	50,79	18,72	25,10	16,71	34,03
production of food products, beverages and tobacco products	14,10	48,01	22,73	19,38	19,77	62,80
textile production, production of clothes, leather, leather products and other materials	22,55	42,63	18,16	24,54	20,04	40,41
wood processing and production of wood products, except furniture	14,63	32,68	34,23	9,94	35,78	36,21
pulp and paper production;	18,28	50,53	64,33	26,04	57,68	44,09
publishing activity	15,17	32,20	31,86	7,07	24,96	35,31
production of coke, oil refining products	11,81	54,52	26,78	23,57	26,57	39,11
chemical and petrochemical industry	793,52	40,83	274,78	52,17	254,63	79,46
production of basic	13,04	23,70	43,83	14,37	40,95	38,86
pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations	13,16	53,86	17,65	33,44	17,79	51,51
production of rubber and plastic products, other non-metallic mineral products	43,50	60,17	65,50	67,11	60,08	62,43
metallurgical production, production of finished metal products, except for the production of machines and equipment	24,53	15,90	24,46	20,02	25,09	32,12
production of computers, electronic and optical products	11,49	28,58	25,49	18,67	24,23	28,50
production of machines and equipment	18,60	32,70	24,24	29,74	20,96	59,21
production of electrical and electronic and optical equipment	18,32	23,50	51,74	13,34	39,00	51,76
production of transport equipment	14,90	55,66	31,50	10,13	31,34	28,69
other industries	36,96	44,09	66,66	5,20	40,83	27,57

Source: Calculated by the authors

The next stage involves the calculation of the root mean square deviation, which allows you to get an idea of how large the data fluctuations are (Table 5).

Next, to model the management of financial evaluation of the economic and innovative activities of industrial enterprises in the conditions of digitalization, the management of professional development projects and the formation of a marketing strategy, we will determine the total distance between the performance indicators of the industrial sectors of Ukraine.

At the next stage, there is a need to calculate the deviation of the activity indicators of the i -th industry from the benchmark, 2012–2022 (Table 7).

And finally, we determine the taxonomy coefficient, which is the result of the calculation of the management modeling of the financial evaluation of the economic and innovative activities of industrial enterprises in the conditions of digitalization, management of professional development projects and the formation of a marketing strategy.

Thus, we have proposed a methodology for modeling the management of financial evaluation of

Table 7. Determination of the deviation of the activity indicators of the i-th industry from the benchmark, 2012–2022

Галузі	4. Deviation of indicators of the i-th industry from the standard					
	Number of innovatively active industrial enterprises (units)	Costs for innovation of industrial enterprises (thousand UAH)	Number of industrial enterprises that introduced innovations (units)	The number of names of innovative types of products introduced by industrial enterprises (units)	The number of industrial enterprises that implemented innovative products (units)	The amount realized innovative products (thousand UAH)
Mining industry	0,264	0,193	0,205	0,345	0,228	0,163
Processing industry, including	0,352	0,183	0,299	0,259	0,316	0,223
production of food products, beverages and tobacco products	0,343	0,189	0,272	0,294	0,291	0,165
textile production, production of clothes, leather, leather products and other materials	0,273	0,200	0,304	0,262	0,289	0,205
wood processing and production of wood products, except furniture	0,337	0,228	0,223	0,407	0,218	0,217
pulp and paper production;	0,303	0,184	0,163	0,255	0,172	0,197
publishing activity	0,331	0,230	0,231	0,479	0,260	0,219
production of coke, oil refining products	0,374	0,177	0,251	0,267	0,252	0,209
chemical and petrochemical industry	0,047	0,204	0,080	0,181	0,083	0,147
production of basic	0,357	0,267	0,197	0,340	0,204	0,209
pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations	0,355	0,178	0,308	0,225	0,307	0,182
production of rubber and plastic products, other non-metallic mineral products	0,198	0,169	0,162	0,160	0,169	0,166
metallurgical production, production of finished metal products, except for the production of machines and equipment	0,262	0,324	0,263	0,290	0,259	0,230
production of computers, electronic and optical products	0,379	0,243	0,257	0,300	0,264	0,244
production of machines and equipment	0,300	0,228	0,264	0,239	0,283	0,170
production of electrical and electronic and optical equipment	0,302	0,268	0,182	0,353	0,209	0,182
production of transport equipment	0,334	0,175	0,232	0,403	0,233	0,243
other industries	0,215	0,197	0,160	0,555	0,204	0,248

Source: Calculated by the authors

Table 8. Determination of the ratio of the management taxonomy of financial evaluation of economic and innovative activities of industrial enterprises, 2012–2022

Industries	5. Taxonomic index of activity of branches (taxonomy coefficient)					
	Number of innovatively active industrial enterprises (units)	Costs for innovation of industrial enterprises (thousand UAH)	Number of industrial enterprises that introduced innovations (units)	The number of names of innovative types of products introduced by industrial enterprises (units)	The number of industrial enterprises that implemented innovative products (units)	The amount realized innovative products (thousand UAH)
Mining industry	0,736	0,807	0,795	0,655	0,772	0,837
Processing industry, including	0,648	0,817	0,701	0,741	0,684	0,777

production of food products, beverages and tobacco products	0,657	0,811	0,728	0,706	0,709	0,835
textile production, production of clothes, leather, leather products and other materials	0,727	0,800	0,696	0,738	0,711	0,795
wood processing and production of wood products, except furniture	0,663	0,772	0,777	0,593	0,782	0,783
pulp and paper production;	0,697	0,816	0,837	0,745	0,828	0,803
publishing activity	0,669	0,770	0,769	0,521	0,740	0,781
production of coke, oil refining products	0,626	0,823	0,749	0,733	0,748	0,791
chemical and petrochemical industry	0,953	0,796	0,920	0,819	0,917	0,853
production of basic	0,643	0,733	0,803	0,660	0,796	0,791
pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations	0,645	0,822	0,692	0,775	0,693	0,818
production of rubber and plastic products, other non-metallic mineral products	0,802	0,831	0,838	0,840	0,831	0,834
metallurgical production, production of finished metal products, except for the production of machines and equipment	0,738	0,676	0,737	0,710	0,741	0,770
production of computers, electronic and optical products	0,621	0,757	0,743	0,700	0,736	0,756
production of machines and equipment	0,700	0,772	0,736	0,761	0,717	0,830
production of electrical and electronic and optical equipment	0,698	0,732	0,818	0,647	0,791	0,818
production of transport equipment	0,666	0,825	0,768	0,597	0,767	0,757
other industries	0,785	0,803	0,840	0,445	0,796	0,752

Source: Calculated by the authors

economic and innovative activities of industrial enterprises in the conditions of digitalization, management of professional development projects and the formation of a marketing strategy. The specified technique will be useful for the effective operation of industrial enterprises in conditions of uncertainty and changes in the external environment.

Conclusions

As a result of the calculations, it is possible to interpret the coefficient of the management taxonomy of financial evaluation of economic and innovative activities of industrial enterprises in the conditions of digitalization, management of professional development projects and formation of a marketing strategy. So, the closer the value of the indicator is to one, the higher the level of economic activity of the industry, in this case in the time dimension.

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